

YOUNG INVENTORS AND PIONEERING INVENTIONS FROM TELEVISION

Baltag O.

Professor Emeritus

Abstract

The work presents chronologically the pioneering inventions of young inventors who determined the development of television. By analysing the patents from the field of television, we found a number four young inventors who were the authors of some inventions which can be considered as pioneering inventions. Brief information concerning inventors' biographies, together with examples of the assigned patents is presented. The following systems have been analysed: mechanic image capture - the Nipkow disk, image dissector tube, wireless image transmission, autofocus system and plasma display. All these had young inventors as authors.

Keywords: mechanic television, image dissector, electronic television, image autofocus, plasma display.

Motto:

1. *One day, Madalina asks: ...how do the thoughts occur to us?*

Looking through the steam of his coffee cup, the teacher remained quiet ... he was thinking ... not even he could remember whence has that thought occurred to him ... was it while gazing the clouds?

2. *The images are similar to reality but not identical to it.*

Introduction

A pioneer patent discloses an invention that creates a new technical field or new technical direction in an existing field.

The Convention of Paris establishes the conditions and effects of claiming a priority with respect to one or more claims filed in or for any state part of the Convention of Paris (1883) or for any state member or the World Trade Organization (1995).

Even if complex, the inventing process can be reduced to two stages: the first phase concerns the conception of the invention, and the second one the reduction of the invention to practice, by filling a patent application. An interesting and, in most cases misunderstood fact: what exactly has stimulated the imagination of some young people without profound studies to imagine or to find basic technical solutions in such a vast field as that of communications through images transmissions? By analysing the beginnings of the research concerning the television systems in patent collections, have been found some young researchers from USA and Europe who had really inventive qualities and filed at national patent offices some technical ideas and solutions which have been fundamental for science development.

The age of these young inventors ranged between 17 and 23 years. They had finished studies corresponding to college, and some of them were students in the first years of some faculties. All of them had knowledge acquired due to the contact with different publications which presented scientific and technical news from Europe and USA. They also have the support of their families which had implanted them the love for science and knowledge. Of course, they had also to face the resistance of specialists surprised to find themselves in the situation to learn and accept new really innovative technical solutions. They had strong characters, were

autodidact, endowed with imagination and the desire to learn more than schools had offered them.

These pioneering inventions appeared in many other fields of science and technique have anticipated and, for some of them, preceded the future field in which both inventors and interested people will be working. For the inventors, these will be "magnum opus" no matter if they changed or not the world or the field in which they activated.

Some of inventions were so new, that they have only been applied after tens of years. We can remember here the "Nipkow disk" applied after 40 years in England, Wolfke "wireless telescope", appeared practically at the same time with the first telegraphic signal transmitted by Marconi though ether, the "Videocaptor devices with Autofocus" appeared in the epoch of TV cameras which used vacuum electronics, "Plasma TV display" also appeared in the epoch of kinescope tubes, the first application appearing after only five years, in 1972 at Mitsubishi and Hitachi.

It is worth noticing the continuous diminution of the duration between invention filing and its industrial application. An exception to these examples is the "dissector" of Farnsworth, an inventor who had the capacity to develop his invention in a pragmatic medium, with an active competition and during an epoch adequate both in terms of technology, and in terms of electronic physics discoveries.

The consecrated term of "television" appears in 1900, being proposed by a physicist, Professor Constantin Dmitrievici Perskyi at the "Congrès International d'Electricité" ("International Congress of Electricity") held in Paris during the period 18th - 25th of August 1900, within the "Exposition universelle internationale de 1900". In this work we shall direct our attention toward some of these young inventors who went beyond their contemporaries with their inventions. Until the year 1900, the technical terminology used for the device which permitted image transmission was the "Electric telescope".

- 1884 - Paul Julius Gottlieb Nipkow, (23 years), Elektrisches Teleskop, DE30105 (C), priority date: 1884-01-06.

- 1898 - Mieczysław Wolfke, (17 years), Прибора для электрической передачи изображений без посредства проводов, Patent rosyjski nr. 4498, 1898-12-24.

- 1927 - Philo Taylor Farnsworth, (21 years), Television System, Patent US1,773,980, Image Dissector, Electronic Television.

- 1965 – Octavian Ioan Baltag, (19 years), patent RO 44277, 1965–06–7, Auto Focus TV Camera; patent RO 50108, 1967-08-17, TV Plasma Display.

1. Paul Iulius Gottlieb Nipkow (22nd of Aug 1860 – 24th of Aug 1940)

Paul Iulius Gottlieb Nipkow was born in Lauenburg (Lebork), Pomerania, as son of Friedrich Wilhelm of casubian origin, a master baker and prime councillor of the city [1].

There are only few information concerning Nipkow's life, because no detailed biography was published, the only information coming from the volume of 100 pages, by Claus Dietrich Scmitt from Stralsund, Germany, an enterpriser born in Lebork, at the anniversary of 100 years from Paul Nipkow's birthday. The first information was given by inventor's descendants.

Figure 1. Paul Iulius Gottlieb Nipkow 1884

During the summer of 1885 he suspended his study due to his father's death. In order to support his family, he finds a job in Eisenbahn-Signalbau-Anstalt in Berlin-Borsigwalde. On the 12th of December 1885 he gets married with Sofia Colonius, his colleague from University, as his daughter was to be born two weeks later. After one year in office, on the 1st of October 1886, the Eisenbahn-Signalbau-Anstalt Company from Berlin-Borsigwalde employs Nipkow on a position of production engineer in railroad signalization field.

One does not know what exactly has determined the interest for image transmission, but it is possible for this subject to exist in the mind of all those who had more or less contact with the new accomplishments carried out in the area of wire communication field: the telegraph and the telephone. Probably, like everybody, he was also dreaming to remote image transmission.

After so many years since his invention, it is natural that legends and stories be born about the origin of an idea. Surprising informations can be found in the interview taken to him by Karl Heinz Norweg [3], appeared in *Neues Wiener Journal*, Wien, 23rd of August

After Nipkow's death, his daughter Emma gathered in some suitcases all the documents, notes and correspondences remained from her father. Many years later, Klaus Nipkow, inventor's nephew allowed her to study them. From the gathered information, he managed to write about the family in which the inventor of Nipkow disk was born. Scmitt stated that Paul Nipkow was a modest, diligent man, endowed with a remarkable imagination, who left behind him 32 inventions [2].

In 1880 we find him as a pupil of the secondary school from Neustadt (Wejherowo). In 1882 being a student at the Friedrich Wilhelm University from Berlin, he attended the courses of physiologic optics with Hermann von Helmholtz and of electric engineering with Adolf Slaby, one of the T.S.F. pioneers of the Technical Institute of Charlottenburg. He studied the telecommunications techniques with Professor Zetzsche, who founded in 1880 the journal *Elektrotechnischen Zeitschrift*.

1930, with the title "*Beim Vater des Fernsehens - Was der siebzigjährige Paul Nipkow erzählt*". One of the toys which generated optical illusions was a disk having a spiral drawn on it, probably used also as an ornament on the occasion of Christmas. According to his memories, it is said that he had such an ornament which, by spinning, suggested him the idea to analyze an image through the holes that passed periodically in front of a window.

It is impossible to describe the mechanism through which the solution of an idea is incubated in a mind before its arousal. After only one year, in 1884, at the age of 24, he handed in at the Imperial Patent Office from Berlin a patent application for a device named "*Elektrisches Teleskop*", according to the terminology used in those years for image transmission. Thus, in 1885 (15th of January) the patent number 30105, Class 21- Elektrische Apparate, for "*Elektrisches Teleskop*", is assigned to him with priority from the 6th of January 1884, the very date when he handed in the application.

Figure 2. Patent Elektrisches Teleskop 30105.

Possibly, young Nipkow was also preoccupied, like many researchers of that time, with the problem of communication by means of images, such that we can situate the “incubation” period during the short years as a student, as preceding the moment of “illumination” concerning the technical solution. In 1885, after the patent having been assigned he publishes in *Elektrotechnische Zeitschrift*, 6, 1885, 419 - 425, the work “*Der Telephotograph und das elektrische Teleskop*” concerning the telephotography [4]. The published work roused the interest of the scientific world, as Paul Clemencau, in a work concerning the stage of image transmission, quotes Nipkow among others, describing in details the proposed solution. [5]

One does not know for sure the reasons that he did not applied his idea immediately, even if there were already technical premises to use it. In the interview given in 1930, Nipkow stated that he was in a precarious material situation, such that he was forced to abandon his patent after only one year, for having not paid

the taxes, thus losing the right to make a business with his invention.

The idea that stood at the basis of his invention (patent) consisted in exploring the projection of an image using a disk endowed with pin holes at a certain distance from each other, along a spiral trajectory that closed a 360° arc. By turning around the disk, each pin hole explores the image along a circular arc which constitutes “*ä line*” of the image, and then the next pin hole situated at a distance equal with its diameter, explores the next line, and the process goes on until the last pin hole of the spiral passed. In this way, the disk generates a series of luminous sequences shaped like circular arcs corresponding to the explored segment of the image, the optical image being transformed by means of a photoelectric sensor in another sequence of electric signals.

Nipkow disk was accepted by the scientists interested in image transmission only after the success of Bird’s experiments in England. It is possible that losing the protection of his patent became the reason to stimulate its utilization by other scientists.

Figure 3. John Logie Baird demonstrates a prototype of his mechanical television system -1924.
(https://www.gebseng.com/publications/reset_the_apparatus_excerpt_big_paul.pdf)

The impact and the echo of the work published by Nipkow concerning the method of image exploration by using his disc was quite special, being quoted and used by numerous researchers both in Europe and USA. A synthesis of researchers' works is presented in the following list, inspired by the documentation of Professor Andree Lange [6].

- Seeing by Electricity, *The Electrical World*, New York, November, 14, 1885,
- In 1891 Henry Sutton, Australia proposes an improvement of Nipkow's system,
- In April 1887, professor Maiss presents Nipkow's invention at Deutscher Polytechnischer Verein from Prague (Prager Tagblatt, 21. April 1887),
- J. Hafner presents Nipkow's invention at the conference of office workers from Royal and Imperial Pstei by using the German term for television, namely "Fernsehen (Der Bautechniker, Wien, n.32, 12. August 1887, p.417),
- In 1888 an article appears correcting the term used by Nipkow: Wallentin I.G., ueber das Fernsehen mittelst Elektrizität mit besonderer Berücksichtigung des "elektrischen Teleskope" von P. NIPKOW, (Centralzeitung für Optik und Mechanik, 9, 1888, 97-101)
- The Freeman's Journal from Dublin shows that Edison researches are already overtopped by Nipkow's invention
- Raphael Eduard Liesegang used for the first time also the name "ferssenhem" in German language (a name that is also used at present) and described Nipkow's invention in the work Beiträge zum Problemen des elektrischen Fernsheen,
- *Zeitschrift für Elektrotechnik*, is sceptic about Szczepanik's solution related to his telescop, and refers also to Nipkow electroscope,

- Senlecq, Perosino, Ayrton et Perry, Liesegang, Szczpanik and Nipkow are quoted together in the USA journal Indiana Tribüne, Volume 23, Number 4, Indianapolis, Marion County, 22 September 1899,

- Wolfke, a 17 years young man, proposes in his patent the utilization of a Nipkow disc.
- Constantin Perskyi quotes Nipkow together with other researchers in the report presented at the Congress of Electricity from Paris in 1900.
- Dussaud's telescope uses a Nipkow's disc.

It is interesting that Nipkow disc was used after 40 years in an intelligent manner by John Logie Baird who makes in February 1924 the first demonstration in England of a mechanic television system, a system which later was used in the whole Europe and USA. Other television pioneers, such as Karolus in Leipzig in 1924, Jenkins in USA in 1923, and Kerkhof from Holland in 1927, have also proved the simplicity of the solution invented 40 years ago. After the appearance of the electronic television, Nipkow disc was used for scanning television movies until the year 1943. The solution was not forgotten. The electronic television had hardly making its first steps, but well-known companies, such as Philips, Telehor, RCA Corp., Zeiss, Marconi Wireless Telegraph Co., Siemens & Halske, etc., did not expected; they filed and obtained tens of patents which made use of Nipkow disk under various versions and technical solutions.

This was really a *pioneering invention* in a quite new field of communications: the television of the first half of the 19th century! Nipkow disc enters in the inventors' attention, each of them trying to obtain more performing apparatuses and images with highest sharpness possible. The disc was the only practical, simple and efficient solution until the 30's, when the electronic television started to compel recognition, the epoch of the mechanic television fading away.

After having occupied some engineer jobs and retired, Nipkow dedicated himself to perfect his invention. So, in 1930 he is assigned the patent no. DE498415 (C) entitled *Einrichtung zur Erzielung des Synchronismus bei Apparated zur elektrischen Bildue-*

bertragung” [7] for synchronization in image transmission systems; priority Patent from 1924 is purchased by Siemens & Halske Co. Between 1924- 1939 are assigned several patents concerning image electric exploitation and transmission.

Figure 4. Paul Nipkow 75 Years (<https://alchetron.com/Paul-Gottlieb-Nipkow>).

After almost half of century since his invention, Paul Nipkow gets back to the world attention, the “Paul Nipkow” radio station being set up. The station emitted daily since 1935 within the ultra-short wavelength band. On the 22th of March 1935, three years after BBC, in Berlin start regular transmissions of *Fernseharbeitsgemeinschaft*” television station that uses a version of Nipkow disc. The new (Nazis’) regime reevaluates Nipkow’s activity; he was designated as honorary president of a new television society *Fernseharbeitsgemeinschaft*”, a station set up under the auspices of *Reichsrundfunkammer* and was later used for Nazis’ propaganda [8]. On this occasion, Paul Nip-

kow is named “great national inventor”, being compared with Gutenberg in term of value. On reaching the age of 75 years, Figure 4, the Goethe University from Frankfurt granted him the title of “*Doctor Honoris Causa*” for his scientific activity. In 1937, his native city Lauenburg declared him as “*Honorary citizen of the city*”. Paul Nipkow died in Berlin on 24th of August 1940 and was buried in Pankow cemetery.

Other modern and actual applications appeared worldwide in this field, having a high specificity as microscopy, multispectral diffraction analysis, optical confocal measurement systems, scanning microscope, drug scanning device, confocal scanner, etc. Figure 5.

Figure 5. Patent KR101471638B1 - Method of pin hole alignment for nipkow disk - Google Patents.

After many years, the Zeiss Company uses the disc in a contemporary technological variant in high definition co-focal microscopy.

After a period of almost 50 years of silence, Paul Nipkow was rediscovered in the years 30s of the past century by journalists and by the Nazis who made use of his fame in politics. Inventor’s personality imposes

even now through the presence of his name in some literary works, TV serials, cultural projects [9] etc. Here are some of them:

- the inventor is quoted in an episode from the television serial *Secret Army*, as the only television inventor by the main character, *Standartenfuhrer Kessler*, a Nazi officer in this fiction, inspired by the period of

German occupation and of the Belgian Resistance. The serial is the work of Gerard Glaister. It was co-produced by BBC and the Flemish Television BRT and broadcasted for three seasons (1977- 1979);

- Nipkow disk appears in Thomas Pynchon novel [10] *Against the Day*, Viking, New York, 2006;
- Gebhard Sengmüller, an Austrian artist who works in the field of mass-media technology, has an initiative inspired from "media archeology" that has developed in 1992 projects and installations inspired from media history. A new project inspired by Nipkow personality is presented in the booklet entitled *Big Paul* [11], from which we present here some fragments:
 - "Big Paul is a functional electro-mechanical television system, which retains the original Nipkow

Disk, but enlarges it to a diameter of two meters, thus substantially increasing the number of transmittable image lines and the achievable image resolution. This means that, for the first time, a system of television is created that retains Nipkow's original idea, but allows it to function in contemporary quality. At the same time, I show an apparatus that—like cinema film and the phonograph, but unlike electronic television —can be comprehended and immediately experienced by viewers."

- Nipkow disc appears in a composition signed by the sketcher Roger Leyonmark in the year 2002, referring to an interplanetary communication system Figure 6, [12].

Figure 6. Illustration.

2. Mieczysław Wolfke (29 May 1883 - 5 mai 1947)

The author of the first patent filed in Russia was a pupil aged 15! He was 17 years old at the moment when the patent was assigned. This happened at the moment when the term "television" was not even known. Two more years will pass until another Russian, Constantin Perskyi, will propose in 1900, its utilization all over the world.

The Polish Society of Physics, the University of Technology from Warsaw, the Physics Committee of the Polish Academy of Science and the Polish Society of Photonics announced that the year 2022 will be dedicated to Mieczyslaw Wolfke [13]. This is an homage

dedicated to an extraordinary scientist at 75 years from his death and 100 years after he was appointed as professor at the University of Technology from Warsaw, thus ensuring the perpetuation of his place in the Parthenon of great Polish scientists.

The life of a strong character [14], an agitated personality in continuous motion, both at the University and in partisans fight for Poland liberation. He left the image of a man of the world, devoted completely to the search of answers and solutions to the world mysteries and utilization of its secrets to develop technologies and to make humanity dreams come true.

Figure 7. Mieczysław Wolfke, 1900, [14].

Figure 8. Mieczysław Wolfke, 1925, [14].

He was born on Polish ground and sleeps his eternal sleep in the heart of Europe, in Swiss. His name: Mieczysław Wolfke, born on the 29th of May 1883 in Lask. His father Karol Juliusz Wolfke, was a road engineer from Warsaw, graduate of the Mine Academy from Sankt Petersburg, and his mother Luycina, born Koźmiński [15], was the sister of the physicist Gustaw Kozminski, student of Mendeleev and Helmholtz. The engineer Karol Wolfke worked not only to improve the condition of the roads which, despite the fact that were paved, got washed by each rain in such a measure, that it was quite impossible to drive on them. He also was responsible for other aspects of city development: he supervised the utilization of lighting with oil in the square, water supply and waste water removal, as well as works related with the reconstruction of damages caused by fire, by using materials more expensive yet also more resistant to weathering.

When Mieczysław was 8 years old, his family moved to Czestochowa. This was the result of Karol Wolfke promotion, who was appointed as coordinator of the engineers who worked in the district of Czestochowa. Living in a city incomparable bigger than Lask was an opportunity for development not only for him, but also for his son.

Wolfke spent those years in Czestochowa. This was one of the first cities from Poland where electricity has reached not only in factories, but lighted also the houses and Virgin Mary Boulevard that goes to Jasna Gora Monastery. At that time the Warsaw - Vienna railroad was equipped also with a telegraph network.

Mieczysław's father, Karol Wolfke, worked as one of the city engineers. Accordingly, he often read articles and news about scientific and technical discoveries in papers which he brought home, together with other news from the factories of the city. What else can be more interesting for a child in love with science and

technology? Impressive, wonderful news! This atmosphere inspired the young boy to dream and try to make his dreams come true. No doubt, the childhood atmosphere, the discussions had a great influence on the interests and hobbies of Mieczysław Wolfke as a child. There have been anecdotes about the idea of him being a "marvel child in the field of physics experiments".

While still a child, he decided that "the only purpose of his life will be to establish communication with other planets, and mainly with the Moon. This decision might have been taken by a boy fascinated by Joule Verne's popular novels, as well as by famous works by Flammarion. Even if today it sounds like a childhood fantasy, the twelve years old boy began to start up his intention. A manuscript of twenty pages entitles "Planetostat" dated in 1895, was meant to lead to the design of a space ship. It is interesting that both, Constantin Tiolkowski (of polish origin) in 1903, and Herman Oberth in 1923, proposed solutions similar with those from "Planetostat" manuscript.

In 1895, Marconi transmitted successfully telegrams using electromagnetic waves generators. Only one year later, in 1896, the press reported information concerning the patent of a Polish man, Jan Szczepanik concerning the image transmission. Only three years later, in 1898, young Mieczysław prefigures and finishes another idea concerning remote mage transmission. In this context predominated by tendencies of the application of new technologies in communications, the invention of Mieczysław Wolfke aged 15, completed the panel of the new visions.

Probably prompted by and with financial support of his father – who was touched by his son performances - the patent application for *wireless telescope* was handed- in on November 1898 at the Patent office from Russia. The Russian patent no. 4498 was assigned to him on the 30th of November 1900 and it has a wide

on the technique of transmission and reception antennas, as in Wolfke patent.

In May 1930 Professor Boris Rosing [16] published in *Electricestvo* Journal a paper related to the contribution of Russian scientists to the development of television. The work reappears published in French in the journal *Revue Generale de Electricitee* from 1932. The invention is forgotten for a long period and it is not known if it was a source of inspiration for other patents.

REPUBLIQUE FRANÇAISE.

OFFICE NATIONAL DE LA PROPRIÉTÉ INDUSTRIELLE.

BREVET D'INVENTION.

XII. — Instruments de précision, électricité.

N° 424.344

8. — LAMPES ÉLECTRIQUES.

Lampe électrique à vapeurs métalliques.

MM. KARL RITZMANN, MIECZYSLAW WOLFKE et FRANZ LISSY résidant en Allemagne.

Demandé le 21 novembre 1910.

Déposé le 11 mars 1911. — Publié le 10 mai 1911.

Figure 11. Patentschrift 55637

At the University of Wrocław, Wolfke worked in Otto Lummer' team, at the generalization of Abbe theory of optical images for nonlinear networks. In 1909, together with Karl Ritzmann, a patent have been assigned to him for a cadmium- mercury lamp. Subsequently, he sold his rights related to the exploitation of his patent to Carl-Zeiss Jena Company, where he worked for one year after getting his Doctor's degree. In 1910 he received the title of Doctor in Physics with a thesis about the definition of optical systems. In 1922, after having returned to Poland, Mieczysław Wolfke, Figure 9, approached the low temperature problem.

He had the first fundamental ideas related to *holography*. When he received the Nobel Prize for researches in holography in 1971, Denis Gabor said that he was not aware of the researches of Mieczysław Wolfke who had proposed this method in 1920. Wolfke had made experimental researches, but the lack of a laser-type radiation source hindered him to obtain notable results [24]. In his work „Über die Möglichkeit der optischen Abbildung von Molekulargittern“, Wolfke presented the very first concept about holography in the world. In 1924 he goes to Leiden at the Institute of Low Temperatures”, where he works with Professor Heik Kamerlingh Onnes, and then with Willem Keesom; he proposed the experiments which led to the discovery of two liquid forms of helium and to liquid helium solidification under pressure. He was the first to remark the *super-fluidity* phenomenon, but neither Wolfke, nor Keesom have capitalized the results. The phenomenon was studied thoroughly later by Piotr Kapica, who was distinguished with the Nobel Prize.

During the period when he worked in Zurich, he was in straight connection with the most eminent scientists of the world. Among others, he was a friend of Albert Einstein, with whom organized concerts at home (Einstein played at violin and Wolfke at piano). It is worth mentioning that just before the war he warned against nuclear guns, and in 1945 he published a booklet about the atomic bomb.

Abramson [17] mentioned it in the chapter referring to “*Early Schemes and Inventions*” from the volume “The History of Television” printed in 1887.

After finishing his studies, being employed in physics researches, his inventory activity has not ceased; Wolfke, together with his colleagues, obtained a series of patents in Swiss, England, Germany and Russia, for various gas discharge devices. [18, ... 23].

SCHWEIZERISCHE EIDGENOSSENSCHAFT

EIDGEN. AMT FÜR

GEISTIGES EIGENTUM

PATENTSCHRIFT

Nr. 55637

24. November 1910, 8 Uhr p.

Klasse 115 e

HAUPTPATENT

Karl RITZMANN, Dr. Mieczyslaw WOLFKE, Breslau, und Franz LISSY, Kattowitz (Deutschland).

Elektrische Metallampflampe.

Figure 12. Patent France 424.344

In 1927 Wolfke worked on the dielectric constant of the liquid helium, and in the next year on the association of liquid dielectrics. He also started the cooperation with the Polish army in the Scientific and Consultative Committee.

In 1936 he verified the electric conductivity of liquid helium and began to organize the Institute for Low Temperatures from the University of Technology from Warsaw.

During the occupation, Wolfke was the manager of the Research Institute of Technical Physics from the University of Technology from Warsaw (controlled by the occupant) and gave lectures at the State Institute for High Technique. He also organized the support for conspiring activities.

After Poland regained its independence, Wolfke came back to Warsaw and contributed to the reconstruction of Polish science; he worked as a Professor at the University of Technology, where carried out researches on low temperatures and held popularization conferences. On the 4th of May 1947 he died suddenly at Zurich and was buried at Sihlfeld cemetery.

Mieczysław Wolfke belonged to many different organizations and associations, for example: Academy of Technical Sciences, Commission of the International Institute of Refrigeration, Warsaw Scientific Society, Polish Physical Society, Polish Academy of Learning in Kraków, Deutsche Physikalische Gesellschaft, Schweizerische Physikalische Gesellschaft, Prussian Academy of Sciences, Warsaw Polytechnic Society, Polish Society of Scientific Expeditions, International Cryogenic Commission, French Physical Society, Swiss Physical Society, Polish National Committee of the International Physical Society, Physical Education and Applied Sciences Committee, YMCA and the Grand National Assembly [25].

Wolfke life was full of love for science, but also of obstacles set by the fate. Forgotten after his death, the youngest inventor from the history of television, whose **pioneering invention** was applied many years later, he did not live to see the recognition of his works

and performances. Unfortunately, this was not a rare situation in the history of Polish [26] and universal science.

3. Philo Taylor Farnsworth (19 Aug. 1906 - 1971)

Philo Taylor Farnsworth was born on the 19th of August 1906, in Indian Creek hamlet near Beaver, Utah, in a Mormon community, being the eldest child among the two sisters and two brothers. His parents were Edwin Farnsworth and Serena Amanda Bastian. In 1918 his family moves to Rigby Idaho, where his father works at a farm. This was an important moment, because the farm had electricity produced by a Delco generator. In 1923 the family moves from Rigby to Provo – Utah, to permit children's access to university studies. Thus, before graduating the Rigby High School, helped by his Chemistry teacher Justin Tolman, he was admitted as a student with a "special status" at the University Brigham Young, where he studied only for two years, suspending his studies after his father death.

Accordingly, he had to work to support and help his family. Being a diligent young man, Farnsworth

graduated two years of studies of algebra and one year of chemistry during one year at Rigby High School, together with other postal studies organized by "National Radio Institute". Next year he worked as assistant electrician and followed other four years of postal studies also at Utah University. He was a precocious child, passionately fond of technical news read in the magazines that he found in the house, then from those subscribed to his family, became fascinated by television, a subject which he had in view and developed all his life.

Even if it seems a legend, Professor Justin Tolman declared at a trial from 1934 between *Farnsworth Corporation* and RCA, that Farnsworth has priority in terms of inventing the electronic television, bringing as a testimony a sketch which he preserved even since the discussions he had when he was at school with the future inventor. It is possible that the way in which he imagined the image exploration was inspired, according to the testimonies of some surviving relatives, by the image of the linear furrows formed after farming works [27, 28].

Figure 13. Philo Taylor Farnsworth at his San Francisco electronics laboratory (https://www.theepochtimes.com/philo-farnsworth-historys-forgotten-inventor-of-television_4252208.html).

Even if undeclared, at the end of the 20' of the XX century, there was an intense activity in Europe and the United States for the realization of an electronic system that shall use "the cathode rays" to catch and reproduce the television images. Such studies were made with promising results by Max Dieckmann during 1925-1928, Philo Farnsworth, Figure 13, in 1927 and Vladimir Zworykin in 1929 at Westinghouse.

The Professor Max Dieckmann and the student Rudolf Hell from the University of Munchen, filed in

1925 (the 5th of April) a patent application at the German Patent Office, for an electronic device destined, as follows from the claims and drawings, to transform the photo-electric image obtained by projecting an object on a photoelectric layer which is explored periodically by an electron fascicle displaced through electric or magnetic fields perpendicular to each other [29], Figure 14. There is no information referring to the physical realization of such a device for electronic image catching.

Aug. 26, 1930.

P. T. FARNSWORTH

1,773,980

TELEVISION SYSTEM

Filed Jan. 7, 1927

4 Sheets-Sheet 1

Figure 14. Patent US 1,773,980

In 1926, at the age of only 20 year, Farnsworth sets up a "Company for television experiments". He is helped by George Everson and Leslie Gorrell, whom he convinced to enter a partnership in order to produce his television system. Farnswort marries Pem Gardner on the 27th of May 1926, and a day after the two leave to California; they moved to San Francisco, where he is helped by Everson, who borrows funds from Crocker First National Bank from San Francisco, and finds a location for a laboratory to continue the researches.

On the 7th of January 1927 he files the first patent for "Television System" [30], a patent granted in 1930. It is interesting that the application was signed two weeks before, on the 21st of December 1926 in San Francisco, California. The patent is granted on 26th of

August 1930 with the number 1,773,980. This patent will change for some years the manner in which the television image is caught and transmitted. This was the first patent which permitted physical realization of an electronic system for image catching by using a new principle applied in the tube called *dissector*. A new era was beginning, that of transmission through electronic exploration of televised images. In 1937 Farnsworth obtained another patent for perfecting the dissector tube [31]. After many, many years, in 1961, ITT published a theoretical study of the phenomena from the dissector tube [32]. The tube is presented in figures 3 and 4. The tube operation is reproduced from the patent in the next paragraph.

Figure 15. Dissector Tube

"The light sensitive plate 6 or cathode of the cell is preferably made flat and is formed of a fine mesh screen 8, and said screen 8 is covered or coated with a light sensitive material such as sodium, potassium, or rubidium. 10 is the anode of the photo-electric cell positioned at the other end of the cell. Between the sensitive plate 6 and anode 10 and closely adjacent to anode 10 is placed an electric shutter 11 formed by a metallic plate in which there is a small aperture 12. Between the shutter 11 and light sensitive plate 6, four plates 13, 14, 15, and 16 are placed at right angles to each other and out side the path of electrons from the plate 6 to the shutter 11. Each opposed pair of the plates are connected to a source of electrical potential of a different frequency. The photo-electric cell should be highly evacuated, such for example as to 10 cm mercury to permit a high potential across the cell without ionization.

The necessity for employing a high potential across the cell arises from the fact that the photoelectrons emitted from the cathode 6 have a small emission velocity which depends upon the color of the light causing their emission. This emission velocity is

Figure 16. Dissector Tube, section.

always small, of the order of that which an electron would acquire by falling through a volt or two, but it may have nearly any direction. This haphazard motion tends to distort the electric image and is only prevented from doing so by making the potential between the cathode 6 and the anode 10 high enough to insure that the time taken for an electron to traverse the distance between cathode 6 and anode 10 is so small that the Small velocity transverse to this path produces no appreciable distortion. Hence the vacuum in the photo-electric cell 7 should be the highest obtainable. The electrical potentials are provided by an oscillator 17, capable of developing two different high frequency electrical currents.

Said oscillator 17 not only is required to provide a source of oscillating energy but is required to provide a form of oscillating energy, the wave form of which is composed of substantially straight lines, as will be hereinafter pointed out. Such a wave form is essential to accomplish a uniform lighting of all portions of the image which is to be produced.."

Figure 5 presents an image of the dissector tube

Figure 17. Image Dissector (https://ethw.org/File:Farnsworth%27s_Image_Dissector.jpg).

The materialization of the ideas was not simple. He needed a vacuum devices, equipment for processing and voiding the glass tube that contained the electrodes and the photosensitive layer of the future dissector tube. With the help of his wife Elma, (also known under the name Pem) and her brother Cliff, Farnworth designed and built all the components - from voided transmission tubes which constituted the scanner of the caught images, emitter and receiver. In this way he created his first television system. The key invention was the camera he invented, named "Image Dissector", Figure 17.

The first dissector tube had a phosphor photo-cathode and had a very small sensitivity; for this reason, the scene needed to be enlighten with high energy sources which heated the people and the scene. Improvements brought to photo cathode by using high sensitivity structures permitted the subjects to stay in front of the TV camera for a long time. Pem, Farnworth wife, was the first human subject whose face was transmitted by electronic television system.

On the 7th of September 1927 they made the first electronic transmission. The first demonstration for the press was carried out in September 1928. The success

of the transmission stimulated so much the bankers from the Crocker First Bank, that they were interested to sell Farnworth company to a bigger bank; they chose the Radio Corporation of America – RCA- who had Vladimir Zworykyn on the position of chief of the researches in the development of a television system. It is interesting that Zworykyn, who worked at his iconoscope, was so thrilled with the quality of the image obtained with dissector tube, that the offer was to buy the dissector tube, offer refused by Farnworth.

In 1929 some of the bankers who invested in research set up a company named *Television Laboratory Inc.* and Farnworth was appointed as vice president and research manager.

In 1931 Farnworth joins *Philadelphia Storage Battery Company (Philco)* that was the producer of radio sets; the association broke up in 1933.

In 1937 Farnworth, who had set up his own company named *Farnsworth Television*, concluded an agreement with *American Telephone & Telegraph (AT&T)* regarding the mutual licencing of the patents of the both companies. In 1938, supported by the agreement of his partner AT&T, Farnworth Television was reorganized under the name *Farnsworth Television and Radio* and purchased the phonographs factory *Capehart Corporation* from Fort Way, Indiana, in order to produce both devices, the radio sets production having to begin in 1939.

RCA, which was from the very beginning interested in Farnsworth researches, did not give up its initial intensions and started a long series of attacks in trial court, meaning to invalidate Farnsworth patents. It was an adequate moment, because Zworykin had developed a new image catching tube, namely iconoscope, but was hindered in its development, because many of the elements necessary for a television system had been patented by Farnsworth. Finally, in 1939 RCA agreed to pay Farnsworth royalties for his patents. The years of

intense work and the trials marked inventor's life, such that in 1939 Farnsworth moved in Maine, to recover himself after depression. The World War stopped the television development in America; yet Farnsworth re-oriented and set-up the "*Farnsworth Wood Production*", a society that manufactured boxes for ammunitions.

In 1947 he came back to Forth Wayne, and in the same year Farnsworth Television produced its first TV set. Yet, the company had deep financial problems and was taken over by "*International Telephone & Telegraph (IT&T)*".

In 1949 this was reorganized as *Capehart - Farnsworth*, Farnsworth being research vice-president. *Capehart-Farnsworth* produced television sets until 1965, but it was a small producer, as compared to RCA.

After having sold his company, Farnsworth continued his researches in the area of new technologies, like radar, infrared telescope and nuclear fusion. He moved back to Utah in 1967 to coordinate the Laboratory of fusion at Brigham Young University. In the next year the fusion laboratory moved to Salt Lake City, operating as *Philo T. Farnsworth Association*, until 1970. Farnsworth, who had accumulated severe debts, was forced to cease his researches. He died of pneumonia on the 11th of March, 1971 at Salt Lake City, Utah.

Pem Farnsworth spent many years trying to revive her husband's heritage that faded away to a great extent as the result of his long judicial battles with RCA. According to his wife, Pem Farnsworth: "*Phil saw the television as a wonderful instrument of teaching. There could not be any excuse for illiteracy. Parents could learn together with their children. The news and the sport events could be seen as they happen*". She added: "*Symphonies would mean more when one could see the musicians playing, and the movies would be seen in our own dining rooms. If we should understand them better, the differences could be solved around conference tables, without starting a war*".

Figure 18. Postal stamp 1983

In 1944 Farnsworth received the first golden medal awarded by the National Association of Television Radio diffusers, in appreciation for his pioneering work. During his life, he also received titles of honorary Doctor in Science from Indiana Technical College (1951) and Brigham Young University (1968). Posthumous, in 1983, the inventor was commemorated on a 20 cents postal stamp with his image, Figure 18, and by introducing him in the National Inventors Hall of Fame in 1984. The Philo T. Farnsworth Memorial Museum was dedicated to his honour in Rigby, Idaho, in 1988.

There is a statue of Farnsworth, the father of electronic television, Figure 19, at Letterman Digital Arts Center from San Francisco. In onoarea sa, Academia de Arte și Științe - Televizoare (ATAS) ca parte a Premiilor Primetime Engineering Emmy, fondeaza premiul *Philo T. Farnsworth Award* necompetitiv prezentat de *Academy of Television Arts & Sciences (ATAS)* as part of the *Primetime Engineering Emmy Awards* ca parte a *Premiilor Primetime Engineering Emmy* pentru „O agenție, companie sau instituție ale cărei contribuții de-

a lungul timpului au avut un impact semnificativ asupra tehnologiei și ingineriei televiziunii” [33].

In his honour, the Academy of Arts and Science - Television (ATAS), establishes, as part of Primetime Engineering Emmy Awards, the non-competitive *Philo T. Farnsworth Award*, presented by *Academy of Television Arts & Sciences (ATAS)* as part of the *Primetime Engineering Emmy Awards* for a company or institution whose contribution along the time had a significant impact on television technology and engineering” [33].

In 1928 Pem, Figure 20, was to become the first woman photographed with the electronic television,

Figure 19. Philo Farnsworth Statue

Farnsworth is quoted in all the works and encyclopaedias concerning the history of television [34...38].

A fabulous life of a young man aged 21, self-educated, who gave the world two **pioneering inventions** “*Dissector Tube*” and *the first integrally electronic television system*.

4. Octavian Ioan Baltag (12 July 1945 –)

This inventor was born in Bucharest, Romania and graduated the Faculty of Physics at the “Al. I. Cuza “University of Iași in 1971. He was a researcher in the domain of magnetometry of small fields and electromagnetic detection at the Centre of Technical Physics of Iași until the year 2000, then he worked as a Professor at the Faculty of Medical Bioengineering of

(<http://cdn.preterhuman.net/texts/unsorted/Television%20Pioneer%20Elma%20Farnsworth%20Dies%20at%2098.htm>).

Several years later, in 2002, she was acclaimed at the EMMY Awards. She lived till the age of 98 years and spent the last 40 years of her life trying to regain the Philo’s reputation that rightfully belonged to him. On the 7th of September 1927, after the first transmission, Phylo and Pem Farnsworth became together the mother and the father of the electronic television.

Figure 20. Elma and Philo Farnsworth

“Grigore T. Popa” University of Medicine and Pharmacy from Iași, where he developed the bioelectromagnetism as a teaching and research field. He recorded the first magnetocardiogram in Romania using a SQUID-type complex installation. He was a doctorship supervisor in Physics at the Doctoral School of the Faculty of Physics from Iași. In 1990, in order to capitalize his inventions, he set up the company “Terraflux Control Ltd”, and in 2010 he set up the Foundation “Romanian Institute of Inventics” from Iași - “IRIIS”- together with a group of inventors. He works in the field of electromagnetic security and bioelectromagnetism.

Figure 21. Octavian Baltag
(1965 year)

4.1. The invention of Auto Focus TV Camera - 1965

During the 60's, the TV cameras were not fitted with autofocus systems. Some of them had an analogue instrument that indicated the high frequencies content corresponding to image sharpness. The application of the autofocus in photography was also impossible, given the technological level at that time. The solution of processing an image element, a segment of the TV signal line, permitted to interpret the video signal and to make decisions concerning the optic system control such that to produce a sharp image. Therefore this system behaves like an extreme adjustment loop. We shall present in the following the description of the patent and the block diagram, Figure 22, of the patent solution.

The image sharpness analysis appeared in the classical photo cameras – with film – later, during the years 80's of the last century. Until that moment, the image focussing in the plane of the photographic film was carried out by establishing the distance through various methods, IR triangulation, and optic or by ultrasound detection up to the plane of interest of the photographed scene.

The solution proposed in 1965 consisted in the analysis of the contrast, by comparing neighbouring portions of the zone of interest and modifying the focussing according to an extreme position where the contrast had a “maximum maximorum” value, moment when the image had maximum sharpness and the television camera could transmit. The maximum contrast was detected electronically, together with the adequate order given to the execution element, namely an actuator / electric engine. The system worked like the eye in an automated adjustment regime, with the detection of the maximum value from a series of intermediary values.

The table presents chronologically the evolution of the automatic control systems of the image focussing used by various companies in photographic apparatus with films.

At the beginning, the only electronic systems used to catch the images, were only those from video cameras used in television. The first portable video cameras that used an electronic system for image catching and exploitation appeared later, during the years 80's.

Year	Firm	Camera name	Principle
1963	Canon	Prototype Photokina`63	UN
1965	Baltag	No name Patent RO 44,277	CD
1971	Nikon	Prototype	UN
1972	Nikon	Lens Nikkor 80	UN
1975	Hengniweier Co.	AF telemetry devices	T, VAF
1981	Honeywell	Patent US 4247762	CD

CD – Contrast Detection; UN – Unknown; T – Triangulation, VAF - Visitronic Auto Focus.

The novelties are usually difficult to perceive by people, the response being most often the refuse to accept the new solutions and ideas. The same happened at the meeting with somebody from the leadership of the Romanian Television. The discussion carried out at Romanian Radio-Television with an engineer, who was the chief of the Technical Direction and of a collective dealing with innovations and inventions, did not help in any way the young inventor. The interlocutor was so surprised by the idea of the automatic focussing, that he started to hit his writing table with his hand, saying plainly in high voice “*this cannot be!*”, and, to be

more convincing, he called an engineer and asked him to show how a television camera works, somewhere through the television stages and laboratories.

The Direction for Technics - Innovation from the Romanian Radio Broadcasting and Television inform that it is not interested in the realization and utilization of the invention. Other referents from the Cinematographic Studio are sceptical with regard to the solution and applicability of the idea. This was quite clear, because the solution concerned the videocaptor cameras endowed with electronic systems for image catching. Hence it was necessary to analyse an electronic signal

corresponding to an electronic image. Confronted with this refusal, the author receives an appreciation transmitted through a letter of the director Sergiu Huzum.

This was the head manager of the “Sahia Cinematographic Studio” and the inventor of a cinematographic effect named “travelling” or “trans-trav”. The effect applied initially in cinematography, extended also in the television production; it is also known as “dolly effect, dolly out, vertigo effect, vertigo zoom, Hitchcock zoom”, being used by different producers. He was preoccupied by the same problem: how to maintain the focussing during trans-focussing! This

was the problem: to maintain the focussing of the plane of interest of the scene during trans-focussing! This was a visionary idea materialized only after more than 20 years, through electronic means, in fact equally visionary as the idea of automatic focussing in itself. Yet, following these refusals of application, after the reviewers analysed the proposed solution, OSIM decided to grant the applicant the invention patent No. 462777 dated the 9th of July 1966. This is the merit of OSIM, who had a politics of supporting new technical solutions and ideas.

Figure 22. Block diagram of the invention, patent RO 44,277 /1966.

The patent application was filed on the 7th of June 1965 at the Romanian Office for Patents and Marks, named OSIM Bucharest. We give here a fragment from the description of the technical solution of the patent entitled [39... 43]: Videocaptor Devices with Autofocus”.

“The convergence of the video camera objective 1 is modified in a certain direction by a servomotor 2, which also implies the modification of the sharpness of the image formed in the camera; this image is explored and the obtained video signals are derived in a derivation circuit 3. The obtained derivatives pass-through two-level discriminator 4 and 5 that memorize the derivative negative and infinite values (of very high value, exceeding a prescribed level), the signals obtained at the output of the discriminator are stored in a memory 6; these signals belong to an image of a certain sharpness. After this first exploration of the image and video signal processing, another similar

operation is performed, this time on an image of another sharpness, obtained by shifting the objective; the video signals corresponding to the same zone of the image obtained at the output of the discriminator 5 pass together with the corresponding signals from the memory 6 in another discriminator, where the derivative amplitudes are compared; the discriminator allows to pass only the derivatives with amplitudes higher than their correspondent (the derivatives will belong to either the first or the second image). The circuit 8 establishes the sense of modification of objective convergence or position with respect to the image plane that is situated on the front face of the video camera.”

Figure presents the diagram corresponding to two raster images; the first image is out-of focus, and the second image is correctly focused. In the diagram one can see the shape of the corresponding video signal, together with its derivatives.

Figure 23. Diagram of the video signals.

Figure 12. Patent RO 46,277

The analyzed video signals are used to control step by step the servomotor such that after the first command and reanalyzing the video signal the shifting sense is established. This shift is performed gradually until reaching the maximum contrast of the video signal, which corresponds to maximum optical contrast. The system operates like a system of extreme automation and adjustment. The advantage of the video signal analysis is that one can select for focusing the segment of the image which is of interest for the operator and the TV transmission. The analysis of the image contrast was used in the photographic and shooting cameras only after the years 80's, when the integrated image sensors of the digital cameras appeared. One can notice the difference between the amplitudes of the derivatives of the two video signals. This patent makes the first mention of the image contrast analysis by means of the corresponding video signal.

Contrast detection operates on the basis of a simple principle resulted from the optics laws, namely that an image is clear when its contrast is optimum.

Therefore, this system must establish the image quality by analyzing the contrast, and the information must be transmitted to the objective to establish its position. In the first moment of the analysis, the system knows neither the image quality (if a correction must be performed), nor the direction to which the correction needs to be made or the value of this correction. Therefore it needs to shift the objective, to establish the necessity of a correction and then to establish if the chosen direction is the right one or it has to be changed. This is a process occurring step by step until the optimum image is determined.

The system is similar in its operation with a biologic system. From a biologic standpoint, image tuning on the retina is possible due to some processes become reflex, which is not controlled consciously. These processes are possible due to the capacity of our brain to compare, differentiate and organize what is transmitted through the eyes. We suppose that this capacity is an evolutive sub-product as the result of cerebral, anatomic and physiologic development together with locomotor system.

Figure 24. Human autofocus

As for the analysis of the image contrast, a first mention of this method appears in the patent application “*Videocaptor devices with automatic focusing*” filed at OSIM (State Office for Inventions and Trademarks) Bucharest on the 7-th of June 1965, 8h 15m; the patent was granted on the 9th of July 1966, with the number 44,277. The patent describes a solution which concerns a **new method** to obtain the image focusing in a camera tube **using the dynamic analysis of the image contrast** in a zone of the taken image selected by the operator.

4.2. The invention of the plasma TV display - 1967

In Romania in the 1960 the research in the plasma field was carried out at the level of basic and fundamental studies, at the Universities of Bucharest and Iasi – Faculty of Physics. The research concerning plasma utilization in the realization of some display devices materialized in the realization, some years later 1980, at IFA Magurele, for some devices for plasma alphanumeric display for applications in computing techniques and measuring equipment.

When come in contact in relation with the anniversary of 50 years since plasma display invention, Larry

Weber, one of the inventors who contributed to the development of TV plasma colour display, declared in a letter from 2014: “*I had no idea that there was Romanian plasma display R&D activity in the 60s*”. The answer took by surprise the professors of Plasma Physics from Iasi, but that was the situation in 60s. “The iron Cortina” was a barrier for the both parties.

The festivity organized by Weber occurred in the context when in 1966 Professor Bitzer from the Illinois University handed in a patent application for a plasma monitor of a computer meant to view logical levels. In fact, he could not find out that at that time, a student from the Physics Faculty was carrying out discharge experiments with some electrodes in a balloon filled with low pressure neon. The experiments materialized in the next year are found in a patent application handed in at OSIM Bucharest for a “*Current- image transducer*”, meant to be used in television to convert video signals to images. In 1972 Mitsubishi (and Hitachi independently) proves the possibility to get images with grey shades using an a.c. controlled display with memory.

Figure 25. Patent RO 59,108, Current - image transducer

The patent with the number RO 50108, Figure 25, [44] was assigned in the same year; it describes a display with plasma and electroluminescent materials, placed in a sandwich-like structure, this being the first

invention from Romania related to plasma utilization in complex devices, such as the television screen [45].

From the description of the invention, we quote the text referring to the drawing, Figure 26 that presents a cross section through the flat screen structure.

ROMÂNIA OFICIUL DE STAT PENTRU INVENȚII ȘI MĂRCI		DESCRIEREA INVENȚIEI 50108	
Perfecționare la invenția nr. _____		Int. Cl. ⁷ : H 01 J 11/00	
Înregistrat: 17.08.1967 Dosar: 54523			
Prioritate: _____			
Publicat în buletinul nr. 6			
Publicat: 1968			
Acordat brevet de invenție, titularului: Balzag Octavian Ioan, Iași		Acordat certificat de autor, autorului: aceiași cu titularul	
(54) Traductor curent-imagine			
(67) Rezumat:			
Prezenta invenție se referă la un dispozitiv de transformare a semnalelor de videofrecvență în imagini luminoase. Traductorul curent-imagine pentru televiziune este alcătuit din:		b - o mască perforată (4) și materialul rezistiv (6) aflat în goulurile amintitei măști;	
a - o rețea de electrozi transparenți (2) pe care este aplicată pelicula de fosfor electroluminiscent (3);		c - elemente neliniare, formate din celulele (5) în care se află un gaz inert și electrozii (8), împreună cu materialul rezistiv (6);	
		d - exploatarea ecranului se face pe diagonală, prin semnale defazate	

Figure 26. Cross section of the TV display

“Current - image transducer”

“The present invention refers to a device that converts the video-frequency signals to light images. The first devices recomposed the image by means of Nipkow’s disk; then it was replaced by the Braun tube used until now, with improvements. These show some disadvantages, such as high voltage supply source necessity, image distortions and a large volume which was one of the hindrances that got in the way of TV receiver miniaturization. In order to reduce the dimensions, the deviation angle was increased but this entailed an increase in geometric dimensions for whose diminution one uses for different methods - not quite efficient. Afterwards, ion traps with electrostatic lenses or permanent magnets were used to reduce the ion spot. In order to reduce the dimensions even more, one resorted to deflection angles of up to 180°; this resulted in the diminution of the image definition and thus, complicated the tube’s construction. The image definition is maximum in the center of the image, and it decreases to the margins. Besides the Nipkow’s disk and Braun’s tube, other devices were proposed, based on the piezoelectric effect and electroluminescence of certain materials, but these proposals did not give satisfactory results, as the contrast and definition were very small. In the following, we describe a device that no longer presents the above-mentioned shortcomings, referring to the figure that represents a cross section with one of the sides. An electroluminescent phosphor film 3 with the thickness of some micrometers is deposited on a grid of transparent electrodes 2; above, this there is a dielectric perforated mask 4, its holes being filled with a resistant material 6. There is then a dielectric plate 7 with grooves 5; in these grooves is an inert gas, and on grooves’ bottom electrodes 8 are placed. Electrodes 2 are covered for protection with a glass plate 1 welded to plate 7. The terminals of electrodes 2 and 8 are pulled out on two of the device’s sides. If one applies on two of the electrodes voltage, exceeding the discharge firing voltage, a free discharge occurs in the gas from the grooves, and the phosphorus becomes luminescent in

the point where the two electrodes intersect, the luminescence increases with the voltage applied on the film’s surface. In order to explore the entire surface, one closes out of the phase signals to electrodes 2 and 8, such that the scanning is carried on the bias. Positive signals are applied on one of the grids and negative signals on the other, both being modulated (to produce grey shades). The device, according to invention, does not need heating sources, such as the classic transducers; it works at much smaller voltages, is practically bi-dimensional with a much simpler structure, does not need high vacuum installation for manufacturing, does not produce pin-cushion or barrel - type distortions, has a constant image definition on the entire screen surface and can be built at any high dimension desired.

Now, after more than 50 years from the first inventions concerning plasma utilization in television, the plasma television sets wait for new solutions to take the place of plasma display, this one entering in history together with forerunners: Nipkow disc, turning mirrors and cathode tube.

Conclusions

Creativity, the process of thinking at new things which have never been performed until that moment, is a complex process, difficult to explain, mainly when reported to certain stages of technics. Creativity is followed by innovation, which “materializes and brings to life” new ideas.

Thus, the invention has a demiurgic character, because it materializes something that has never existed at the moment of its realization and revelation.

Invention and revelation of a technical solution, followed by its materialization, cannot be made without a “minimum minimorum” of specific knowledge and information. The inventors presented here were autodidact; they completed their studies in parallel with their college and university studies.

Their inventions have become “pioneering inventions”, because at the moment when the patents appeared, they presented absolutely new technical solutions. Years after years passed until some other innovative solutions developed from these inventions

appeared. This is the case of “Nipkow disc”, applied only after 40 years, and the television through radio-electric waves. With the evolution of technique, this time delay was reduced to some years, as in the case of “autofocus system” and of “plasma display”.

References

1. https://ro.frwiki.wiki/wiki/Paul_Nipkow.
2. ***, Lębork. Powstała biografia Paula Nipkowa, <https://gp24.pl/lebork-powstala-biografia-paula-nipkowa/ar/4406463>.
3. Lanage A., <https://www.histv.net/nipkow-23-81930>.
4. Nipkow P.G., Der Telephotograph und das elektrische Teleskop, *Elektrotechnische Zeitschrift*, 6, 1885, 419-42.
5. Clemenceau, P., "De la vision des objets a grande distance", *La lumière électrique*, Paris, 5 décembre 1885, pp.433-440.
6. Lange A. <https://www.histv.net/l-impact-du-disque-de-nipkow>.
7. Nipkow P.G., Patent, DE498415 (C), Einrichtung zur Erzielung des Synchronismus bei Apparaten zur elektrischen Bilduebertragung, 1930.
8. Lanage A., <https://www.histv.net/glorification-de-nipkow-par-regime->
9. Lange A., <https://www.histv.net/nipkow-evocations>
10. Solutia Pynchon T., *Against the Day*, Viking, New York, 2006
11. Sengmüller G., Big Paul, A Media-Archaeological Installation by Gebhard Sengmüller, www.gebseng.com.
12. Leyonmark R., Illustration "A proposal for sending and receiving moving-picture signals between the planets Earth and Mars by means of electric telescope", 2002.
13. ***, The-Year-of-Wolfke-Part-1, <https://www.pw.edu.pl/engpw/News/The-Year-of-Wolfke-Part-1-The-precursor-of-television>, accessed November, 2022/
14. Petelczyc K., Kędzierska E., Mieczysław Wolfke Gdyby mi dali choć pół miliona... Biografia, Oficyna Wydawnicza Politechniki Warszawskiej, Warszawa 2018.
15. Łaniecki W., Mieczysław Wolfke 1883—1947, *Kwartalnik Historii Nauki i Techniki*, 1976, T 21, No. 3, pp. 545-553.
16. Rosing B., La participation des savants russes au developement de la television electrique, *Revue Generale d Electricitee*, Paris, Tome XXXI, No. 6, 6 avril 1932.
17. Abramson A., *The History of television, 1880 to 1941*, McFarland & Company, Inc., Publishers, Jeverson, North Carolina, and London, 1987.
18. Wolfke M.: Прибора для электрической передачи изображений безъ посредства проводовъ. Patent Russe, 4498, 24 November 1898. (Patent rosyjski nr 4498, 24 listopada 1898 r.)
19. Ritzmann K., Wolfke M., Lissy F.: Elektrische Metalldampf lampen. Patent szwajcarski, nr 55637, 24 listopada 1910 r.
20. Ritzmann K., Wolfke M., Lissy F., Improvements in Electric Vapour Lamps. Patent brytyjski, nr 27 163, 22 listopada 1910 r.
21. Ritzmann K., Wolfke M., Lissy F., Elektrische Metalldampf lampen, patent CH55637A, 1910.
22. Ritzmann K., Wolfke M., Lissy F., Lampe Electrique a Vapeurs Metalliques, Patent Fracaise 424,344, 1911.
23. Ritzmann K., Wolfke M., Lissy F., Improvement in Electric Vapour Lamps, No. 27,163, 1911.
24. M. Wolfke, Uber die Moglichkeit der optischen Abbildung von Molekulargittern, *Physikalische Zeitschrift*, 21, 495 (1920).
25. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mieczysław_Wolfke#cite_note-12
26. Petelczyc K., Mieczysław Wolfke - a pioneer of holography, *Photonics Letters of Poland*, vol. 13 (4), 66-69 (2021), doi: 10.4302/plp.v13i4.1107.
27. Everson G., *The Story of Television, the Life of Philo T. Farnsworth*, WW Norton & Company Inc. New York, 1949.
28. Webb R.C., *Tele-Visionaries, The people behind the invention of television*, IEEE Press, John Willey & Sons Inc. Publication, 2005.
29. Dieckmann M., Hell R., Lichtelektrische Bildzerlegerrohre fur Fernseher, Patent DE 450187, 1927.
30. Farnsworth P.T., Television System, Patent USA 1,773,980, 1930.
31. Farnsworth P.T., Image Disector, Patent USA 2,087,683, 1937.
32. Belovich J.F., Image Disector Tube, Research Memo No. 336, ITT Industrial Laboratories, April 18, 1961.
33. ***, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Philo_T._Farnsworth_Award
34. Burns R.W., *Communications: An International History of the Formative Years*, IEE, London, 2004
35. Abramson A., *The History of television, 1880 to 1941*, McFarland & Company, Inc. Publishers, Jefferson, North Carolina and London.
36. Marshall P., *Inventing Television*, Thesis, Univ. of Manchester, 2011.
37. Shiers G., *Early Television, A Bibliographic Guide to 1940*, Routledge Taylor and Francis Group, new York and London, 11997.
38. Eckhardt G.H., *Electronic Television, The Goodheart – Willcox Co.mpany Inc.*, Publishers, 1936.
39. Baltag O., Aparat videocaptor cu punere la punct automata, (Videocaptor Devices with Autofocus), Patent RO 46277, 1966.
40. Baltag O., The Automatic Focusing - Hystory, *Romanian Journal of Industrial Property*, no. 3-4, pp. 49-65, 2014.
41. Baltag O., Automatic Focusing - a Romanian Invention, Proc of the 41-st ICOHTEC Symposium "Technology in Times of Transition", pp. 182, Brasov, Romania, 2014.
42. Baltag O., History of Automatic Focusing Reflected by Patents, *Science Innovation*, 2015; 3(1):

- 1-17. Published online March 2, 2015
(<http://www.sciencepublishinggroup.com/j/si>), doi:
10.11648/j.si.20150301.11
43. *** dpreview.com/forums/post/60617042
44. Baltag O., (Traductor curent imagine),
Current- imagine transducer, Patent RO 50108, 1967.
45. Baltag O., The History of Plasma Display Re-
flected by Patents: An Advanced Study, (DOI:
10.9734/bpi/nvst/v4/2559E), Chapter 14 in volume
New Visions in Science and Technology Vol. 4, Editor
Dr. Essam A. Makky, pp. 132-148, DOI:
10.9734/bpi/nvst/v4.